

Mapping Research Topics on the Financial Services Authority (OJK): VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the development of research around the Financial Services Authority. The research was conducted from 2011 to 2022, by searching national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Scopus, and Scopus via the Perish/Harzing application, with the keyword "Financial Services Authority". Based on the search results, there were 548 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a literature review study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to Financial Services Authority is divided into 7 clusters and 206 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a literature review study, there are 5 main themes related to the Financial Services Authority (FSA).

Keywords: Financial Services Authority (FSA), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review

Introduction

The development of society's needs which are increasing every day is one of the impacts of globalization. Society has a future view of life (vision) which is realized to face the increasing and unpredictable demands of life in the future.

This increase has produced a variety of commodities and services that are enjoyed by the public, so that the growth of the Indonesian economic system cannot be separated from developments in technology and economic information. The existence of the Financial Services Authority (OJK) means that all financial services companies (banks, securities trading, guarantee companies) are organized into one body that is responsible for their supervision. OJK is an independent body and does not intervene. OJK was established based on Article 34 of Law No.3 of 2004 concerning amendments to Law No.23 of 1999 concerning Bank Indonesia, with reference to Article 55 paragraph 2 of Law No.21 of 2011 which regulates independent institutions.

Research or publication of scientific journals about OJK continues to increase every year. Based on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garb a), there were 504 journals published between 2012 and 2022. This shows that OJK is developing very rapidly as the only regulatory and supervisory system for activities in the capital markets, banking and financial services sectors. other.

The aim of this research is to determine a map of research development regarding the Financial Services Authority in Sharia Financial Institutions over a period of 10 years. Time period from 2012 to 2022 using bibliometric methods with VOSviewer and literature review studies.

Literature Review

The Financial Services Authority (OJK) was formed based on Article 34 of Law Number 23 of 1999 and became effective on January 1 2013. OJK is tasked with carrying out audits of financial bodies, both banking and non-banking, and has a mission to protect and fulfill the needs of the people, creating consistent and

continuous financial patterns, as well as maintaining regular, honest, accountable and transparent financial patterns.

Bibliometrics is a field of library science that studies research applications implemented with quantitative statistical models. Bibliometrics comes from the words "bible" or "bibliography" and "metrics", which means book and measurement. Therefore, bibliometric techniques are research applications that are applied using quantitative statistical models.

VOSviewer is software used to visualize network maps based on network instructions to view and analyze the map. VOSviewer can be used to create network maps of scientific publications, journals, researchers, analytical institutions, keywords or titles. VOSviewer has three types of visualization, namely network visualization, overlay visualization, and density visualization. VOSviewer can also display specific information from bibliometric graphic maps and show large bibliometric maps to easily interpret the context. VOSviewer is able to display maps with different rules, each emphasizing different dimensions, and has zoom, scroll and search features that make it easier to control the map in detail.

A literature review is a frame of reference, theory or review for analyzing and classifying clues found in a search. The origin of the reference (publication, journal) referred to must be related and current (state of the art) and in accordance with the information contained in the reference literature. The literature review aims to obtain conceptual principles that accommodate the resolution of the obstacles studied. The concepts obtained are the first action for reviewers to better interpret the problems observed in accordance with a valid scientific framework.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object of the research is the Financial Services Authority (OJK). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about the Financial Services Authority (OJK) originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keywords "Financial Services Authority" and "Financial Services Authority" for the entire year period (2012 -2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on literature review studies.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding the Financial Services Authority in Sharia Financial Institutions

A search for scientific journal publications regarding the Financial Services Authority in Sharia Financial Institutions during the 2012-2022 period shows the development of journal publications every year, especially in the last 6 years. Data

was obtained from 548 article titles from accredited national and international journals. Article publications were recorded at 94 articles in 2021, so the typical publication of articles about the Financial Services Authority is more than 40 articles per year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data about the Financial Services Authority by year

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2011	1	2015	28	2019	90
2012	4	2016	48	2020	65
2013	20	2017	52	2021	94
2014	25	2018	67	2022	54
Number of Publication Articles 548					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 2 shows the 10 affiliates/institutions that publish the most research articles about the Financial Services Authority in Sharia Financial Institutions. The Faculty Student Journal Collection is the journal publishing institution that publishes the most research results on the Financial Services Authority, namely 44 articles.

Table 2. Data on institutions and journals publishing Financial Services Authority journal articles

Name of Institution/Affiliation	Number of Publications
Collection of Law Faculty Student Journals	44
Economic Journal	13
Diponegoro Law Journal	12
Private Law Journal	11
Dynamics	10
Student Online Journal (JOM) in the Field of Legal Studies	8
Journal of Business Administration	5
Indonesian Notary	4
Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (Birci-Journal): Humanities and Social Sciences	3
Diponegoro Journal of Management	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 3 shows that the most productive researcher is Bismar Nasution from the University of North Sumatra, who wrote 16 articles.

Table 3. Researcher productivity around the Financial Services Authority

Researcher	Number of Publications
Mustafa (University of North Sumatra), Bismar Nasution (University of North Sumatra), Sunarmi (University of North Sumatra), Muhammad Ekaputra (University of North Sumatra), Teuku Fathir (University of North Sumatra), Putra, Ramli Siregar, M Irwansyah, Indra, Mahmud Siregar, Suhaidi, Sari Rezeki, Widodo Ramadhana, Akmalia Indriana, Firdaus, Muhammad Ekaputra, Yunus Abidin, Murti, Ashri Azhari Baeha (University of North Sumatra),	16

Oktriningsih (University of North Sumatra), Diah Ayu (University of North Sumatra), Dede Aquari Irawan Surbakti, Saryo, Suhaidi, Rebekka Dosma Sinaga

Rusli (Bandar Lampung University), Zulfi Diane Zaini (Bandar Lampung University), Safitri (Bandar Lampung University), Sija Putra Rulanda (Bandar Lampung University), Lukmanul Hakim (Bandar Lampung University), Bismar Nasution (Bandar Lampung University), Mahmud Siregar (Bandar Lampung University), Sunarmi Sunarmi (Bandar Lampung University)

7

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research Regarding Financial Services Authorities in Sharia Financial Institutions

Search results for research articles via the Garuda website (Digital Referral Group) are sent in the form of a Research Information System (RIS), entered and described using VOSViewer. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Depiction of the growth map relationship surrounding the Financial Services Authority

Source: Processed data, VOSViewer software 1.6.18.

The co-word map and the growth of research regarding the Financial Services Authority in Sharia Financial Institutions is broken down into 7 clusters and 206 topics, namely as follows:

- Cluster 1. The color red consists of 57 topics, namely: analysis, asset, bank, bopo, BPR, capital, capital adequacy ratio, CAR, data collection technique, deposit ratio, determination, documentation, economic growth, equity, factor, FDR, financial performance, financing, fraud, fund, growth, independent variable, influence, Islamic bank, Islamic banking, Islamic commercial bank, liquidity, management, NPF, object, research, performance, performing

financing, period, period, population, profitability, purposive sampling, purposive sampling technique, quality, ratio, report, return, risk, ROA, ROE, secondary data, sharia equity fund, sharia mutual fund, sharpe, significant effect, stock fund, technique, treynor, type, year.

- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 41 topics, namely: administrative sanction, AFPI, agent, agreement, capital market, company, concept, debt, effectiveness, fact, financial service author, financial technology, fintech, Indonesia, information technology, investor, issue, issuer, lawsuit, legal certainty, legal consequence, legal protection, legal standing, money, capital market, peer lending, poj, power, profession, protection, regulation, repo transaction, security, society, statute, study, technology, transaction, use, violation.
- Cluster 3. The blue color consists of 41, namely: activity, authority, bank Indonesia, banking, banking sector, banking supervision, central bank condition, cooperation, coordination, country, deposit insurance agency, development, economy, establishment, existence, finance, financial institution, financial service authority, financial service sector, financial services sector, financial system, function, independence, independence, independent institution, institution, investigation, letter, literature, LPD, normative legal research, ojk, ojk law, pension fund, responsibility, scope, sector, supervision, system.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 36 topics, namely: article, bpsk, case, characteristic, community, complaint, consumer protection, context, corporate, decision, dispute relations, document, education, enactment, financial sector, financial services authority regulation, financial services authority regulation number, human research, illegal investment, implementation, interview, issuance, lack, laps, legal material, legal research, legislation, literature study, mechanism, paragraph, principle, provision, public, settlement, sharia principle, source.
- Cluster 5. Purple consists of 19 topics, namely: bmt, business, business license, conceptual approach, control, covid, credit, debtor, government, impact, increase, obligation, obstacle, pandemic, policy, relations, research method, statute approach, substance.
- Cluster 6. Black consists of 6 topics, namely: bankruptcy, financial service, financial stability, insurance, insurance company, investment.
- Cluster 7. The orange color consists of 6 topics, namely: credit unions, pension funds, services, financial services authorities, supervision, banking.

Mapping Literature Review regarding the Duties, Authorities, Functions, Independence and Governance of the Financial Services Authority (OJK)

First, OJK's task is to carry out regulatory, supervisory and audit functions for financial services institutions, and is responsible for ensuring the stability of the financial system and protecting the interests of financial services consumers.

Second, OJK has the authority to regulate, supervise and examine financial service institutions which include banks, insurance companies, reinsurance companies, pension funds, finance companies, financial institutions, securities companies and stock exchanges. OJK also has the authority to grant business permits, determine prudential requirements, take preventive and corrective actions, and take resolution actions for problematic financial services institutions.

Third, OJK has several functions, including: regulatory, supervisory, inspection, education and consumer protection functions.

Fourth, OJK is an independent institution that is directly responsible to the President. OJK cannot be intervened by any party in carrying out its duties and functions.

Fifth, OJK governance is regulated in Law no. 21 of 2011 and its implementing regulations. This governance includes organizational structure, decision-making procedures, appointment and dismissal of leaders, as well as internal and external supervision. OJK also has a Board of Commissioners whose job is to be the highest decision maker and supervise OJK's performance.

Mapping Literature Review regarding the Relationship between the Financial Services Authority (OJK) and other institutions

First, Bank Indonesia. In carrying out its duties, OJK collaborates with BI in monitoring and regulating the stability of the financial system as a whole. For example, BI and OJK have an important role in monitoring risks arising from the banking sector and capital markets, as well as working together to ensure financial institutions comply with existing rules and regulations. Apart from that, BI and OJK also work together in regulating and supervising fintech activities in Indonesia. These two institutions have an important role in ensuring that innovation in the financial services sector can continue to develop and provide benefits to society, while still paying attention to the security and stability of the financial system as a whole.

Second, the Capital Market Supervisory Agency/BAPEPAM. In the context of capital market supervision, BAPEPAM is part of the OJK. In 2011, Law no. 21/2011 concerning the Financial Services Authority combining the functions of BAPEPAM into the OJK. Since then, OJK has had the duty and authority to regulate and supervise the capital market in Indonesia, including licensing and supervision of the institutions involved in it. In practice, BAPEPAM is still often referred to as a separate entity from OJK, especially in terms of direct supervision of companies in the capital market. However, officially, BAPEPAM has now become part of the OJK and is integrated into the larger organizational structure.

Third, the Deposit Insurance Corporation/LPS. In carrying out its duties, LPS collaborates with OJK to monitor banking health and prevent bank failures, supervise banks and ensure that banks comply with applicable laws and regulations, and coordinate with each other in carrying out their respective duties and provide each other with the necessary information. in carrying out his duties.

Fourth, Ministry of Finance/Kemenkeu. The Ministry of Finance and the OJK can also work together in carrying out their duties, such as in terms of supervising banks that are related to managing the state budget or issuing financial instruments by companies registered on the capital market.

Fifth, International Financial Services Institutions/LJKI. In general, LJKI and OJK are related in terms of regulating and supervising the financial sector, however LJKI focuses more on international financial issues, while OJK focuses more on financial issues in Indonesia. These two institutions can also coordinate and work together in developing international standards and promoting the stability of the global financial system.

Sixth, Ministry of Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises. The Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs and the OJK are also working together in efforts to increase financial inclusion among small and medium businesses, by providing training and education regarding financial management and financial access. The two institutions also collaborate in developing financial innovations, such as technology-based financing (fintech), to make it easier for small and medium businesses to access financing sources.

Seventh, Indonesian Capital Market Arbitration Board/BAPMI. BAPMI and OJK are linked in monitoring and strengthening investor confidence in the capital market. BAPMI can assist OJK in resolving disputes that may occur in the capital market, while OJK can provide the necessary guidance and regulations to ensure that BAPMI carries out its duties well. Apart from that, OJK also strengthens BAPMI's

performance through supervision and regulation of BAPMI's activities as an alternative dispute resolution institution in the capital market.

Eighth, Consumer Dispute Resolution Agency/BPSK. BPSK and OJK are interrelated in terms of resolving disputes over financial products or services. If a dispute occurs between a consumer and a financial service provider, the consumer can submit a request for dispute resolution to BPSK. However, if the dispute is related to regulatory issues or financial service providers' compliance with applicable rules, BPSK can submit a report to the OJK as the regulator of the financial services sector.

Ninth, Constitutional Court. Linkages between the Constitutional Court and the OJK can occur when there is a legal dispute relating to the financial sector and regulations issued by the OJK. In this case, the Constitutional Court can be the arbitrator who resolves disputes and determines whether OJK regulations are in accordance with the constitution or not. An example of the relationship between the Constitutional Court and the OJK can occur in cases where the OJK issues new regulations that some parties consider to violate basic or constitutional rights. If the dispute cannot be resolved through mediation or negotiation, the party who feels disadvantaged can file a lawsuit with the Constitutional Court. The Constitutional Court will evaluate the regulations and decide whether the regulations are in accordance with the constitution or not. In this case, OJK must comply with the decision of the Constitutional Court. If the Constitutional Court decides that the OJK regulations are not in accordance with the constitution, then the OJK must cancel or amend the regulations in accordance with the Constitutional Court's decision.

Tenth, Alternative Dispute Resolution Institution/LAPS. OJK can facilitate or recommend LAPS as an alternative mechanism for resolving disputes between consumers and financial services businesses. OJK can also provide supervision over LAPS registered and operating in Indonesia to ensure that these institutions meet the standards set by OJK. In general, LAPS and OJK work together to ensure that financial services consumers receive adequate legal protection and ensure that the financial services industry in Indonesia operates transparently, fairly and safely for consumers.

Eleventh, Notary. In practice, Notaries and the OJK often work together on matters related to the financial services sector, such as in examining documents and financial transactions. The relationship between the Notary and the OJK is important in ensuring that financial services business activities run transparently, fairly, and in accordance with applicable laws and regulations.

Twelfth, the UK's Financial Services Authority. The Financial Services Authority (FSA) is a financial regulator that existed in the UK from 2001 to 2013. The FSA was later replaced by two separate financial regulators, namely the Financial Conduct Authority (FCA) and the Prudential Regulation Authority (PRA). Meanwhile, the Financial Services Authority (OJK) is a financial regulator in Indonesia which was established in 2011 to supervise the financial services sector in Indonesia. Even though these two regulators come from different countries and have different names, they both have the same goal, namely supervising the financial services sector in their respective countries to ensure the stability and security of the financial system. Both also have an important role in ensuring consumer and investor protection, as well as promoting healthy competition in the financial services sector. However, as the FSA no longer exists in the UK and has been replaced by the FCA and PRA, there is no direct link between the UK FSA and the Indonesian OJK.

Thirteenth, Law no. 30 of 1999 in relation to OJK. Relation to the Financial Services Authority (OJK), Law no. 30 of 1999 is the legal basis for the OJK to supervise insurance companies operating in Indonesia. Before the enactment of Law no. 30 of 1999, supervision of insurance companies is carried out by the Ministry of Finance. However, after the enactment of Law no. 30 of 1999, supervision of

insurance companies was handed over to the Capital Markets and Financial Institutions Supervisory Agency (Bapepam-LK), which has now changed to the Financial Services Authority (OJK).

Mapping Literature Review around Resources at the Financial Services Authority (OJK)

First, the online admissions information system uses the Information Systems Success Model. This system was developed by Delone and Mclean. This model consists of six dimensions, namely system quality, information quality, service quality, use, user satisfaction, and individual impact.

Second, internal control over fixed assets and inventories at OJK offices, including: (1) OJK must have clear and documented policies and procedures for managing fixed assets and inventories, including procurement, storage, maintenance and write-off; (2) OJK must ensure that tasks related to the management of fixed assets and inventories are separated between various sections or work units; (3) OJK must strictly monitor the procurement, storage, maintenance and disposal of fixed assets and inventories; (4) OJK must limit access to fixed assets and inventories only to people who need them; (5) OJK must ensure that records relating to fixed assets and inventories are maintained properly and accurately; (6) OJK must select reliable suppliers to ensure the quality and quantity of fixed assets and supplies received; and (7) OJK must maintain fixed assets and inventories periodically to ensure that they remain in good condition and can be used.

Third, the OJK webinar has a theme of smart investment, including: (1) Types of investments available; (2) How to choose the right investment; (3) The importance of diversification; (4) Risk management; and (5) Measuring investment performance.

Fourth, Internal Audit Capability Model for Public Sector/IACM. The Indonesian Financial Services Authority (OJK) uses IACM as a reference for developing internal audit capabilities in the financial services sector. The OJK IACM determines six main domains that must be owned by internal audit in the financial services sector, namely: (1) Governance, Risk and Control/GRC; (2) Government Performance and Accountability/GPA; (3) Strategic Management/SM; (4) Fraud Risk Management/FRM; (5) Information and Communication Technology/ICT; and (6) Human Resource Management/HRM.

Fifth, providing incentives for Risk Weighted Assets/RWA. The Risk Weighted Asset Incentive (RWA) is a policy implemented by the Indonesian Financial Services Authority (OJK) to encourage banks to carry out better risk management. RWA is a way to assess the risk of an asset and determine a certain percentage of capital that must be maintained as a risk reserve. In providing RWA incentives, the OJK provides convenience for banks that have good risk management by providing a reduction in the level of GWM (Minimum Statutory Reserves) and can reduce mandatory reserve requirements. Meanwhile, banks that fail to meet the RWA target will be subject to a risk fee by the OJK.

Sixth, the performance of OJK office employees is seen from various aspects, including: (1) Work ethic; (2) Work discipline; (3) Honesty-Humility personality dimensions with Cyberloafing in employees; (4) Job training; (5) The seriousness of the violation; (6) Leadership style; (7) Demographic factors; and (8) Organizational factors.

Mapping Literature Review regarding the Influence of Financial Services Authority (OJK) Regulations

There are 32 influences of OJK regulations on the financial sector, namely: (1) Application to Murabahah, Mudharabah, Musyarakah, Ijarah, Qardh, Wakalah bil Ujrah products; (2) Regulatory Sandbox in Fintech; (3) Fintech; (4) Banking profitability; (5) Income tax; (6) Repurchase agreement transaction guidelines; (7)

Illegal online lending practices; (8) Economic Growth; (9) Sharia Sukuk/Bonds; (10) Mutual Funds; (11) Credit restructuring and relaxation during the Covid-19 pandemic; (12) Expansion of Multifinance functions; (13) Sustainable business ecosystem; (14) Compensation for unpaid bank customers; (15) State financial regulations; (16) Insurance premiums (life, motor vehicles); (17) Insurance agreements via telemarketing; (18) Utilization of foreign workers; (19) Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR reporting; (20) Customer Due Diligence in Peer-to-Peer Lending; (21) Role of the Sharia Supervisory Board/DPS; (22) Finance companies; (23) Electronic Money; (24) MSMEs; (25) Electronic Banking; (26) Shares; (27) Advance payment; (28) Trading; (29) Officeless financial services; (30) Credit relaxation for subsidized housing ownership; (31) Bad credit with restructuring; and (32) Branchless Banking.

Mapping Literature Review regarding the Functions of the Financial Services Authority (OJK)

First, OJK supervision. There are 19 institutions/agencies supervised by the OJK, including: (1) Conventional Commercial Banks/BUK; (2) Sharia Commercial Banks/BUS; (3) Sharia Business Unit/UUS; (4) Rural Banks/BPR; (5) Sharia People's Financing Bank/BPRS; (6) Baitul Maal wa Tamwil/BMT; (7) Sharia Microfinance Institutions/LKMS; (8) Savings and Loans Cooperative/KSP; (9) Foreign Venture Capital Companies; (10) Real Estate/property companies; (11) Peer to Peer Lending Company; (12) Capital markets; (13) Insurance (Asabri); (14) Market Conduct; (15) Fiduciary guarantee; (16) Providing credit; (17) Pawnshop; (18) Sharia capital market share screening; and (19) Electronic-based lending (peer to peer landing/crowdfunding).

Second, the authority of the OJK. There are 16 OJK authorities regarding several activities in the financial sector, including: (1) Company bankruptcy (insurance); (2) Money laundering crime; (3) Crime of escrow account fraud; (4) Insurance administrative sanctions; (5) State financial system stability committee; (6) Banking customers who violate the precautionary principle; (7) Transfer of shares/acquisition; (8) Fraud in investment business; (9) Security of transactions in the capital market; (10) Fictitious credit; (11) Online fund borrowing; (12) Criminal acts of corruption in banking; (13) Problem loans on People's Business Credit/KUR; (14) Management of sharia pension funds; (15) Consumer financing institutions; and (16) Village Credit Institutions/LPD.

Third, OJK protection. There are 11 protections provided by OJK, including: (1) Deposit customers; (2) Consumer financing; (3) Insurance policy holders; (4) Capital market investors; (5) Illegal/fraudulent/fictitious investment; (6) Customer data; (7) Gold savings; (8) Illegal pawnshops; (9) Equity Crowdfunding Investors; (10) Securities Crowdfunding; (11) Skimming.

Fourth, licensing of Microfinance Institutions/LKM. To obtain a permit as an LKM, prospective LKMs must submit a permit application to the OJK. The application must meet the requirements set by the OJK. Several general requirements that must be met by prospective LKMs are as follows: (1) Prospective LKMs must have legal entity status and be officially registered with the Ministry of Law and Human Rights; (2) LKMs must have basic capital of at least IDR 1 billion for LKMs with a regional or provincial business scale and IDR 500 million for LKMs with a district or city business scale; (3) MFIs must be owned by Indonesian individuals or legal entities; (4) The LKM management must consist of people who meet the requirements such as high integrity, experience in the financial sector, and relevant educational background; and (5) MFIs must have an adequate risk management system. After fulfilling these requirements, prospective MFIs will be tested for suitability and suitability by the OJK. If the prospective LKM is declared to meet the requirements, OJK will grant a business permit to the LKM to carry out

business activities as a microfinance institution. MFI license holders must continue to comply with the terms and conditions set by the OJK. If an MFI violates the stipulated provisions, the OJK can revoke the MFI's business license.

Fifth, revocation of business permits by OJK. One of OJK's duties is to grant and revoke business permits to companies operating in the financial sector. OJK can revoke a business license if the company violates the rules or regulations set by the OJK. Some examples of violations that could result in the revocation of a business license include: (1) Failure to comply with applicable regulations in the management and storage of customer funds; (2) Failure to report data and information required by OJK within the specified time; (3) Not having sufficient capital to run a business in a healthy and sustainable manner; (4) Being involved in acts of fraud or embezzlement of customer funds; and (5) Does not have an adequate internal control system to prevent financial and operational risks. If the OJK revokes a company's business permit, then the company is no longer permitted to carry out its business in the financial sector and must immediately stop its operational activities. This aims to protect customers and prevent greater losses. Apart from that, OJK can also hold companies that commit violations to be legally responsible.

Sixth, dispute resolution by OJK. One of OJK's duties is to resolve disputes that occur between consumers and the financial institutions it supervises. Dispute resolution by the OJK can be carried out through several mechanisms, including: (1) Mediation, namely a dispute resolution process involving a neutral third party to help the disputing parties reach a mutual agreement, where the OJK can facilitate mediation between consumers and financial institutions in dispute; (2) Arbitration, namely the process of resolving disputes outside the court carried out by one or a group of arbitrators who are considered neutral and have the authority to issue binding decisions, where the OJK has the authority to appoint arbitrators in the arbitration process between consumers and financial institutions; and (3) Settlement in Court, namely if mediation and arbitration efforts are unsuccessful, OJK can recommend dispute resolution through court, where OJK can also provide legal assistance and assistance to consumers who choose to take the court route. In resolving disputes between consumers and financial institutions, OJK will pay attention to the principles of justice and consumer interests and ensure that the financial institutions it supervises fulfill applicable legal and regulatory obligations.

Seventh, OJK investigation. There are several cases, including:

- (1) Capital market. OJK investigations into capital markets can be carried out in various forms, such as routine supervision, investigations into suspected violations, as well as overall capital market risk assessments. In carrying out investigations, OJK can collaborate with other parties such as the Police, Prosecutor's Office, or the Capital Market and Financial Institutions Supervisory Agency (Bapepam-LK). Some examples of OJK investigation cases in the capital market in Indonesia include the alleged insider trading case at PT Hanson International Tbk in 2018, as well as the alleged stock manipulation case at PT Kimia Farma Tbk in 2020. Through this investigation, the OJK aims to ensure that market players capital acts fairly and transparently, thereby increasing investor confidence and strengthening overall capital market stability.
- (2) The investigatory authority of Civil Servants (PNS) carries out investigations into banking crimes. According to Article 10 paragraph (1) of Law Number 31 of 1999 concerning the Eradication of Corruption Crimes, investigators are civil servants who are authorized to carry out investigations into criminal acts of corruption. However, to carry out investigations into banking crimes, there are more specific regulations governing this matter. Article 43 paragraph (1) of Law Number 21 of 2011 concerning the Financial Services Authority states that investigations and inquiries into criminal acts in the banking sector are

carried out by authorized law enforcement officials, namely the police and prosecutors. Thus, civil servant investigators do not have the authority to carry out investigations into banking crimes, unless there are elements of corruption that can be handled by corruption investigators.

Eighth, levies by the OJK on the obligations of the capital market notary profession. OJK (Financial Services Authority) is an institution responsible for supervising and regulating activities in the financial services sector in Indonesia, including the capital market. OJK has the authority to levy levies on the obligations of the capital market notary profession. Capital market notary professional fees are fees paid by parties who use notary services to carry out transactions in the capital market. This fee aims to finance OJK supervision and regulation in the capital markets sector. This levy is regulated in Article 78 paragraph (1) of Law Number 8 of 1995 concerning Capital Markets, which states that notaries who issue securities transaction deeds are required to levy fees determined by the OJK. The amount of capital market notary professional fees is regulated by the OJK in applicable regulations. This fee is usually calculated based on a percentage of the value of transactions carried out in the capital market. So, in conclusion, the OJK has the authority to collect levies on the obligations of the capital market notary profession as a fee to finance the OJK's supervision and regulation in the capital markets sector.

Ninth, bank rescue by Statutory administrators. Saving banks by Statutory administrators at the OJK refers to the efforts of the Financial Services Authority (OJK) to save banks experiencing financial difficulties by implementing a bank management scheme called the Statute. Statute is an abbreviation for ' State-Owned Bank Restructuring Scheme ' or state-owned bank restructuring scheme. This scheme is implemented by the OJK to improve the financial performance of state-owned banks that are experiencing difficulties, especially those caused by management problems, bad credit, or other factors. In the Statutory scheme, the OJK acts as a temporary manager of troubled banks, by maintaining the continuity of bank operations and carrying out restructuring efforts to improve the bank's financial performance. OJK will appoint a management team consisting of skilled financial and management professionals to manage the bank and create a restructuring plan. The restructuring plan created by the management team will include various actions, such as improving bank management, reducing operational costs, increasing income, improving credit quality, and selling unproductive assets. OJK can also provide bailout funds or additional capital to help banks overcome their financial difficulties. In this case, the OJK's main goal is to ensure the survival of banks and protect customers and the financial system from greater losses. Apart from that, OJK also seeks to strengthen the banking sector as a whole by ensuring financial stability and banking health in Indonesia.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding the Financial Services Authority (OJK) during the period 2011 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 548 research articles.
- In the mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research developments regarding the Financial Services Authority (OJK) are divided into 7 clusters and 206 items. Cluster 1 consists of 57 items, cluster 2 consists of 41 items, cluster 3 consists of 41 items, cluster 4 consists of 36 items, cluster 5 consists of 19 items, cluster 6 consists of 6 items, cluster 7 consists of 6 items.
- Based on the literature review, there are 5 main research themes surrounding the Financial Services Authority, namely: (1) Duties, authority, functions,

independence, governance; (2) OJK's relationship with other institutions; (3) Resources at OJK; (4) Influence of OJK regulations; and (5) OJK functions.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- The results of the literature review study can be explained in a more complex way.

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